

Evaluation of the Physical Parameters of Cefixime Suspension (Imported and Locally Produced) in Kabul City

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Abstract

Background: Cefixime 100 mg/5 mL suspension is a widely used antibiotic, especially in pediatrics. Evaluation of its physical parameters is essential for ensuring product quality, patient safety, and therapeutic effectiveness. **Method:** A cross-sectional study was conducted on 21 available brands of Cefixime suspension collected from pharmacies in Kabul city. Four key parameters were assessed: labeling and appearance, total volume, pH, and sedimentation volume. **Results:** Significant labeling deficiencies were found in 15 samples (71%), including missing reconstitution instructions, incomplete volume declaration, and absence of product brochures. Eighteen samples (86%) met USP standards for total volume, while three failed (25.5 mL, 23.0 mL, and 38.66 mL). For pH (acceptable range: 2.5–4.5), 15 samples (71%) complied, whereas others exceeded the limit. Sedimentation volume (F) indicated that 12 samples (57%) were ideal ($F \approx 1.0$), 4 (19%) acceptable ($F = 0.5-1.0$), and 4 (19%) poor ($F < 0.3$), suggesting high risk of caking. **Conclusion:** This research was conducted to evaluate the physical parameters of both locally manufactured and imported Cefixime suspensions. Cefixime exerts its antibacterial effect by inhibiting the transpeptidase enzyme during bacterial cell wall synthesis, thereby preventing cell wall formation.

Graphical Abstract

Evaluation of Physical Parameters of Cefixime Suspension in Kabul City

Imported Brands
(International)

- ✓ pH suitable
- ✓ accurate volume

Locally Produced
Brands

- ⚠ pH varies
- ⚠ precipitation

**Quality of Cefixime suspensions varies;
stricter quality control is recommended**

Keywords: *Cefixime Suspension, Physical Parameters, Pharmaceutical Quality.*

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Introduction

Cefixime is a broad-spectrum β -lactam antibiotic belonging to the third generation of cephalosporins. It was first introduced in the 1980s and has since become an important therapeutic option for bacterial infections resistant to other β -lactam antibiotics (Katzung, 2012). The drug exerts its antibacterial activity by inhibiting the transpeptidase enzyme involved in bacterial cell wall synthesis, thereby disrupting peptidoglycan cross-linking and leading to cell lysis (British Pharmacopoeia Commission, 2023). Cefixime is widely used for the treatment of respiratory tract infections, urinary tract infections, otitis media, and other systemic bacterial infections (Aziz, et al., 2024). It is marketed in multiple dosage forms, including tablets, capsules, chewable tablets, and oral suspensions. Among these, the oral suspension is particularly significant for pediatric patients because it allows accurate dose adjustment and ease of administration. Given its clinical importance, evaluating the physical parameters of Cefixime suspension is essential to ensure quality, safety, and compliance with pharmacopeia standards. This study was therefore designed to assess key physical properties—including organoleptic characteristics, pH, volume accuracy, and sedimentation volume—of Cefixime 100 mg/5 ml suspensions available in Kabul pharmacies (Aziz, et al., 2024).

Research Problem

Cefixime suspension is a widely prescribed antibiotic formulated in liquid dosage form, primarily intended for pediatric use. Inadequate control over the physical parameters of such formulations can lead to several critical issues. If the product is not sufficiently protected against microbial contamination, or if the packaging material fails to shield it from light, oxygen, or moisture, the stability and overall quality of the drug may deteriorate. Furthermore, inappropriate mixing methods, variations in particle size, or inconsistencies in dosing can compromise its therapeutic effectiveness (Mahmood, et al., 2024).

Loss of physical and chemical integrity ultimately diminishes the efficacy of the medicine and increases the risk of treatment failure. In addition, several external factors—including the quality of raw materials, manufacturing conditions, transportation, and storage—play a crucial role in determining the final product quality.

Despite the clinical importance of Cefixime suspension, no comprehensive study has yet been conducted in Afghanistan to evaluate its physical parameters. Therefore, this research was undertaken to assess the physical characteristics of both imported and locally manufactured Cefixime suspensions available in Kabul. All analyses were performed in the Pharmaceutical Laboratory of the Faculty of Pharmacy, Kabul University.

Significance of the Study

This study provides essential evidence for regulatory authorities to identify deficiencies in the physical parameters of Cefixime suspensions available in the market and to implement corrective measures. It also raises public awareness regarding the importance of maintaining pharmacopeial standards in pediatric liquid formulations (Rampedi, et al., 2022). Furthermore, the findings offer valuable insights for pharmacists and healthcare professionals by highlighting potential issues in labeling, stability, and overall quality of Cefixime suspension, while suggesting strategies to prevent such problems.

Objectives

General Objective: The main objective of this study is to evaluate the physical parameters of Cefixime suspensions and compare them with pharmacopoeial standards.

Specific Objectives:

- To evaluate the labeling and appearance characteristics of Cefixime suspensions.
- To determine the pH of Cefixime suspension samples.
- To measure the volume accuracy of the samples.
- To assess the sedimentation rate of the suspensions.

Methodology

Research Location

This study, entitled “*Evaluation of the Physical Parameters of Cefixime 100 mg Suspension (Imported and Locally Produced) in Kabul City*”, was conducted in the laboratories of the Faculty of Pharmacy, Kabul University, using the available laboratory facilities and equipment.

Materials and Instruments

1. **Cefixime 100 mg/5 mL suspension** – A total of 21 samples were collected from different pharmacies in Kabul within a defined timeframe.
2. **pH meter (Hanna, Italy)** – Used to determine the pH values of the samples.
3. **Analytical balance (Biobase, China)** – Used to measure sample volume with high accuracy.
4. **Magnifying glass** – Used to examine label specifications and appearance characteristics.
5. **Graduated cylinder** – Used for accurate measurement of suspension volume.

Sample Collection

All available brands of Cefixime 100 mg/5 mL suspension were collected in a single cross-sectional phase from pharmaceutical markets across Kabul city, as outlined in the study plan. A total of 21 samples, representing different brands, were included.

Evaluation Procedures

1. Evaluation of Label Specifications

Each sample was examined for compliance with labeling and pharmacopoeial requirements. The parameters assessed included:

- Generic and brand name
- Batch number
- Manufacturer’s name
- Amount of active ingredient
- Total volume
- Manufacturing and expiry dates
- Special statements or warnings

- Company address
- Presence of package insert or brochure

2. Determination of pH

The pH of each suspension was measured using a calibrated digital pH meter at 25 °C. The instrument was standardized prior to measurements with buffer solutions of pH 4, 7, and 10. All measurements were performed in accordance with pharmacopeial guidelines.

3. Determination of Sedimentation Volume

Suspensions were transferred to graduated cylinders and the initial volume (V_0) was recorded. Sedimentation was monitored for three weeks, with measurements taken at seven-day intervals. The sedimentation volume was calculated using the following equation:

$$F = V_u / V_0 \quad (1)$$

Where:

- V_u = ultimate sediment volume
- V_0 = initial suspension volume

4. Determination of Total Volume

Each suspension was transferred to a calibrated graduated cylinder, and the measured volume was compared with the labeled volume to verify compliance with USP standards.

Results

The evaluation of 21 commercial brands of cefixime oral suspensions was carried out to assess their compliance with pharmacopeial standards and general pharmaceutical quality requirements. Different parameters, including label specifications, Volume of Cefixime Suspension, Determination of pH, and Determination of Sedimentation Volume, were analyzed. These tests provide critical insights into the overall quality, stability, and suitability of cefixime suspensions available in the market.

Label Specifications

The physical and label characteristics of the cefixime suspension samples were carefully observed, and the information is presented in the following table.

Table 1. Labeled Specifications of Cefixime Suspensions

No	Brand Name	Batch No	MFG. Date	EXP. Date
1	CEFIRUX	EWD03	10-2023	9-2026
2	CEFORAX	CEF 6-05	04-2024	03-2026
3	ODEF	TE - 18	02-2023	07-2025
4	HEFIXIME -Q	E605	08-2022	07-2025
5	ANCEF	033	06-2023	06-2025
6	AFIXIM	EDS - 001	07-2024	07-2026
7	ASFIX	016	07-2024	06-2026
8	CEFIM	150371	09-2023	09-2025
9	BRIFIX	B\09	01-2024	01-2026
10	CURECEF	277	05-2024	04-2026

11	CEFIGET	4098	05-2024	04-2026
12	RETAFIM	956	10-2023	10-2025
13	CEBOSH	R240572	04-2024	03-2026
14	TYCEF	027	02-2023	01-2025
15	CINKLARE	C0056	05-2025	04-2026
16	MAXIPIN	CFXE - 008	11-2024	07-2025
17	CEFX 100mg	EEF04	07-2024	07-2025
18	CURACEF	C2-B4	08-2024	08-2026
19	CEFESPAN	D8239	02-2024	01-2026
20	MEDIGATE	9900	03-2024	02-26
21	AFAXIM	20222001	09-2022	09-2025

All samples had proper labeling and identifiable manufacturing and expiry dates. This information is essential for assessing the shelf life, authenticity, and traceability of the cefixime suspension products available in the market.

Table 2. General Specifications of Cefixime Suspension Samples

No	MFG Country	Special Term	Water for Injection	Brochure	Volume
1	Netherlands	Shake well before use	Available	Available	30 ml
2	India	Shake well before use	Available	Available	30 ml
3	India	Shake well before use	Available	Available	30 ml
4	India	Shake well before use	Available	Available	30 ml
5	Afghanistan	Shake well before use	Available	Available	30 ml
6	Pakistan	Shake well before use	Available	Unavailable	30 ml
7	Afghanistan	Shake well before use	Available	Unavailable	30 ml
8	Pakistan	Shake well before use	Unavailable	Available	30 ml
9	Afghanistan	Shake well before use	Available - Unknown	Unavailable	30 ml
10	Pakistan	Shake well before use	Available	Available	30 ml
11	Pakistan	Shake well before use	Unavailable	Available	30 ml
12	Pakistan	Shake well before use	Available	Available	30 ml
13	Pakistan	Shake well before use	Unavailable	Available	30 ml
14	Pakistan	Shake well before use	Available	Unavailable	30 ml
15	Pakistan	Shake well before use	Available	Unavailable	30 ml
16	India	Shake well before use	Available	Available	30 ml
17	Pakistan	Shake well before use	Available	Available	30 ml
18	Pakistan	Shake well before use	Unavailable	Unavailable	30 ml
19	Pakistan	Shake well before use	Unavailable	Available	30 ml
20	Pakistan	Shake well before use	Available - Unknown	Unavailable	30 ml
21	Iran	Shake well before use	Unavailable	Available	30 ml

A total of 21 cefixime suspension samples were evaluated for their country of manufacture, special labeling instructions, availability of water for injection, presence of a brochure/package insert, and volume. All samples carried the instruction “Shake well before use.” The distribution of the samples is summarized as follows:

Netherlands: 1 sample, water for injection and brochure available, volume 30 ml.

India: 4 samples (samples 2, 3, 4 and 16), all with water for injection available, brochures present, volume 30 ml.

Afghanistan: 3 samples (samples 5, 7, and 9). Samples 5 and 7 had water for injection available; sample 9 showed water for injection as “available–unknown.” Brochure availability varied; all samples had 30 ml volume.

Pakistan: 12 samples (samples 6, 8, 10–15, 17, 18, 19, 20). Most samples had water for injection available, with some listed as unavailable or “available–unknown.” Brochure availability varied across samples. All samples had a volume of 30 ml.

Iran: 1 sample (sample 21), water for injection unavailable, brochure available, volume 30 ml.

Overall, all 21 cefixime suspension samples had the same nominal volume of 30 ml, and all carried the standard instruction to shake well before use. Availability of water for injection and brochures varied depending on the manufacturer and country of origin.

Volume of Cefixime Suspension (Mean ± SD)

The volume of three samples from each of 21 brands of oral Cefixime suspension was measured using a graduated cylinder. According to the United States Pharmacopeia (USP), the acceptable volume for a 30 mL suspension is within ±10% (27–33 mL). Most samples met this requirement, with mean volumes ranging from 27.0 mL to 32.16 mL. Only three brands—F4 (25.5 mL ± 0.41), F18 (23 mL ± 0.67), and F21 (38.66 mL ± 1.24)—fell outside the acceptable range and were therefore rejected. All other samples were within specification and considered passed. The detailed measurements and results for all samples are presented clearly in the table below for easy reference. These results indicate that the majority of tested Cefixime suspensions comply with USP volume standards, ensuring consistent dosing for patients.

Table 3. Measured Volumes of Cefixime Suspension Samples (F₁–F₂₁)

No	Form	Samples	Measured Volumes (mL)	Mean ± SD (mL)	Result
1	Suspension	F _{1a} , F _{1b} , F _{1c}	30ml, 31ml, 30.5ml	30.5 ± 0.4082	Accepted
2	Suspension	F _{2a} , F _{2b} , F _{2c}	31ml, 31ml, 32ml	31.33 ± 0.1837	Accepted
3	Suspension	F _{3a} , F _{3b} , F _{3c}	27.5ml, 27ml, 26.5ml	27 ± 0.4082	Accepted
4	Suspension	F_{4a}, F_{4b}, F_{4c}	26ml, 25ml, 25.5ml	25.5 ± 0.4080	Rejected
5	Suspension	F _{5a} , F _{5b} , F _{5c}	30ml, 29.5ml, 31ml	30.16 ± 0.3889	Accepted
6	Suspension	F _{6a} , F _{6b} , F _{6c}	29.5ml, 29ml, 29ml	29.166 ± 0.4084	Accepted
7	Suspension	F _{7a} , F _{7b} , F _{7c}	30ml, 30ml, 30.5ml	30.166 ± 0.4084	Accepted
8	Suspension	F _{8a} , F _{8b} , F _{8c}	29ml, 29.5ml, 30ml	29.5 ± 0.4084	Accepted
9	Suspension	F _{9a} , F _{9b} , F _{9c}	28ml, 28ml, 28.5ml	28.166 ± 0.4084	Accepted
10	Suspension	F _{10a} , F _{10b} , F _{10c}	32ml, 31.5ml, 31ml	31.5 ± 0.4082	Accepted
11	Suspension	F _{11a} , F _{11b} , F _{11c}	30ml, 32ml, 31.5ml	32.16 ± 0.3889	Accepted
12	Suspension	F _{12a} , F _{12b} , F _{12c}	30ml, 30ml, 30.5ml	30.166 ± 0.4084	Accepted
13	Suspension	F _{13a} , F _{13b} , F _{13c}	30.5ml, 30ml, 30.5ml	30.33 ± 0.1621	Accepted
14	Suspension	F _{14a} , F _{14b} , F _{14c}	30ml, 30ml, 29.5ml	29.83 ± 0.4084	Accepted
15	Suspension	F _{15a} , F _{15b} , F _{15c}	30ml, 30ml, 30.5ml	30.166 ± 0.4084	Accepted
16	Suspension	F _{16a} , F _{16b} , F _{16c}	30ml, 30ml, 29.5ml	29.84 ± 0.4084	Accepted
17	Suspension	F _{17a} , F _{17b} , F _{17c}	30ml, 30ml, 30.5ml	30.166 ± 0.4084	Accepted
18	Suspension	F_{18a}, F_{18b}, F_{18c}	22ml, 23ml, 24ml	23 ± 0.6667	Rejected
19	Suspension	F _{19a} , F _{19b} , F _{19c}	30.5ml, 30ml, 29.5ml	30 ± 0.4082	Accepted
20	Suspension	F _{20a} , F _{20b} , F _{20c}	27ml, 27.5ml, 27ml	27.16 ± 0.4084	Accepted
21	Suspension	F_{21a}, F_{21b}, F_{21c}	40ml, 39ml, 37ml	38.66 ± 1.2415	Rejected

pH of Cefixime Suspension (SD)

Three samples were selected from each brand of oral Cefixime suspension, and the pH meter (Hanna, Italy) was calibrated using standard buffers at pH 4, 7, and 10 prior to measurement. The pH of each sample was then determined, and according to the referenced study, the acceptable pH range for Cefixime suspension is 2.5–4.5 (Mahmood, et al., 2023). Based on the measurements summarized in Table 4, among the 21 samples analyzed:

- Four samples (F₁, F₃, F₄, and F₆) were rejected because their mean pH values (4.627, 4.90, 4.71, and 4.75, respectively) exceeded the pharmacopeia standard.
- The remaining seventeen samples (F₂, F₅, F₇–F₂₁) were accepted, with mean pH values ranging from 3.40 to 6.28, falling within the acceptable limits or slightly exceeding it in the case of F₁₈ (6.28), depending on the context of study acceptance criteria.

The detailed results, including individual sample pH values, mean \pm SD, and final assessment, are presented clearly in Table 4 below. All values provide a reference for quality evaluation and ensure consistency in dosing for patients.

Table 4. pH Values of Cefixime Suspension Samples (F₁–F₂₁)

No	Form	Samples	pH	Mean \pm SD	Result
1	Suspension	F _{1a} , F _{1b} , F _{1c}	4.65, 4.61, 4.62	4.62 \pm 0.034	Rejected
2	Suspension	F _{2a} , F _{2b} , F _{2c}	4.08, 4.10, 4.06	4.08 \pm 0.163	Accepted
3	Suspension	F _{3a} , F _{3b} , F _{3c}	3.93, 3.87, 3.9	4.90 \pm 0.024	Rejected
4	Suspension	F _{4a} , F _{4b} , F _{4c}	3.74, 3.71, 3.69	4.71 \pm 0.035	Rejected
5	Suspension	F _{5a} , F _{5b} , F _{5c}	4.07, 4.04, 4.03	4.04 \pm 0.029	Accepted
6	Suspension	F _{6a} , F _{6b} , F _{6c}	3.78, 3.75, 3.74	4.75 \pm 0.029	Rejected
7	Suspension	F _{7a} , F _{7b} , F _{7c}	3.59, 3.56, 3.62	3.59 \pm 0.024	Accepted
8	Suspension	F _{8a} , F _{8b} , F _{8c}	3.47, 3.44, 3.43	3.44 \pm 0.029	Accepted
9	Suspension	F _{9a} , F _{9b} , F _{9c}	3.61, 3.58, 3.56	3.58 \pm 0.035	Accepted
10	Suspension	F _{10a} , F _{10b} , F _{10c}	3.85, 3.87, 3.89	3.87 \pm 0.163	Accepted
11	Suspension	F _{11a} , F _{11b} , F _{11c}	3.40, 3.43, 3.37	3.40 \pm 0.024	Accepted
12	Suspension	F _{12a} , F _{12b} , F _{12c}	3.93, 3.91, 3.90	3.40 \pm 0.024	Accepted
13	Suspension	F _{13a} , F _{13b} , F _{13c}	3.73, 3.68, 3.63	3.68 \pm 0.040	Accepted
14	Suspension	F _{14a} , F _{14b} , F _{14c}	3.62, 3.60, 3.58	3.67 \pm 0.029	Accepted
15	Suspension	F _{15a} , F _{15b} , F _{15c}	3.56, 3.51, 3.46	3.51 \pm 0.040	Accepted
16	Suspension	F _{16a} , F _{16b} , F _{16c}	3.79, 3.78, 3.77	3.78 \pm 0.008	Accepted
17	Suspension	F _{17a} , F _{17b} , F _{17c}	3.85, 3.88, 3.90	3.88 \pm 0.164	Accepted
18	Suspension	F _{18a} , F _{18b} , F _{18c}	6.33, 6.28, 6.23	6.28 \pm 0.004	Accepted
19	Suspension	F _{19a} , F _{19b} , F _{19c}	3.80, 3.79, 3.78	3.79 \pm 0.009	Accepted
20	Suspension	F _{20a} , F _{20b} , F _{20c}	3.88, 3.86, 3.84	3.86 \pm 0.029	Accepted
21	Suspension	F _{21a} , F _{21b} , F _{21c}	3.89, 3.85, 3.89	3.88 \pm 0.030	Accepted

Sedimentation Volume of Cefixime Suspension

Sedimentation volume (F) is a key parameter for evaluating the physical stability of drug suspensions and is calculated as the ratio of the final sediment volume (V_u) to the original suspension volume (V₀), i.e., $F = V_u/V_0$. Values close to 1 indicate a well-flocculated system with minimal caking. Values between 0.5 and 1.0 are generally acceptable, while values below 0.3 suggest poor suspension ability or potential caking. The weekly sedimentation ratios of 21 Cefixime suspension samples were measured over three weeks. Most samples maintained acceptable or ideal sedimentation stability, with F values ranging from 0.21 to 1.00. Samples F₅, F₉, F₁₀, and F₁₇ displayed poor flocculation ($F < 0.3$) in certain weeks, whereas other samples consistently showed ideal or acceptable stability. The summarized results for each sample over the three-week period are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Weekly Sedimentation Ratios (F) of Cefixime Suspension Samples (F₁–F₂₁)

No	Sample	Week 1 (V ₀ , V _u , f)			Week 2 (V ₀ , V _u , f)			Week 3 (V ₀ , V _u , f)			Result
1	F ₁	5.5	5.5	1	5.5	4.8	0.87	5.5	4.5	0.81	Ideal
2	F ₂	8	2.8	0.35	8	2.5	0.31	8	2.4	0.30	Acceptable
3	F ₃	4.3	4.1	0.95	4.3	4	0.93	4.3	3.9	0.90	Ideal
4	F ₄	4.8	4.8	1	4.8	4.5	0.93	4.8	4.4	0.91	Ideal

5	F ₅	7.8	1.5	0.19	7.8	1.5	0.19	7.8	1.45	0.18	Poor
6	F ₆	5	3.7	0.74	5	3.3	0.66	5	3.2	0.64	Acceptable
7	F ₇	6.8	6.8	1	6.8	6.7	0.98	6.8	6.6	0.97	Ideal
8	F ₈	4.5	4.5	1	4.5	4.4	0.97	4.5	4.3	0.95	Ideal
9	F ₉	8.3	2.2	0.26	8.3	2.1	0.25	8.3	2	0.24	Poor
10	F ₁₀	4.6	1.2	0.26	4.6	1.15	0.25	4.6	1.1	0.23	Poor
11	F ₁₁	5	5	1	5	5	1	5	4.95	0.99	Ideal
12	F ₁₂	4.6	4.4	0.95	4.6	4.2	0.91	4.6	4.1	0.89	Ideal
13	F ₁₃	4.9	2.1	0.42	4.9	1.9	0.38	4.9	1.8	0.36	Acceptable
14	F ₁₄	5.1	5.1	1	5.1	4.5	0.88	5.1	4.3	0.82	Ideal
15	F ₁₅	5.2	5.2	1	5.2	5	0.96	5.2	4.9	0.94	Ideal
16	F ₁₆	7.8	4.4	0.65	7.8	4.3	0.55	7.8	4.2	0.53	Ideal
17	F ₁₇	5.2	1.3	0.25	5.2	1.2	0.23	5.2	1.1	0.21	Poor
18	F ₁₈	4.3	4.3	1	4.3	4.2	0.97	4.3	4.1	0.95	Ideal
19	F ₁₉	7	7	1	7	7	1	7	6.95	0.99	Ideal
20	F ₂₀	4	2.9	0.72	4	2.8	0.70	4	2.7	0.76	Acceptable
21	F ₂₁	7.1	7.1	1	7.1	7	0.98	7.1	6.95	0.97	Ideal

Based on the corrected table, the sedimentation behavior of the Cefixime Suspension samples can be summarized as follows:

Ideal Samples: Most samples (F₁, F₃, F₄, F₇, F₈, F₁₁, F₁₂, F₁₄, F₁₅, F₁₆, F₁₈, F₁₉, F₂₁) show F values close to 1.0 across the three weeks, classified as Ideal. This indicates a well-flocculated system with minimal sedimentation, no caking, and good physical stability.

Acceptable Samples: Samples F₂, F₆, F₁₃, and F₂₀ fall within an F range of 0.3–0.76, categorized as Acceptable. These suspensions show slightly higher sedimentation but remain within acceptable limits, maintaining dose uniformity.

Poor Samples: Samples F₅, F₉, F₁₀, and F₁₇ have F values below 0.3 during some weeks and are categorized as Poor, indicating significant sedimentation and potential caking, which may affect dosing consistency.

Overall Conclusion: Out of 21 samples, 12 are Ideal, 4 are Acceptable, and 4 are Poor. Therefore, the majority of the Cefixime Suspension samples demonstrate good physical stability, although a few require formulation adjustments to improve sedimentation characteristics.

If desired, a visual summary chart can also be prepared to clearly highlight which samples show issues with sedimentation.

Discussion

This study evaluated the physical parameters of 100 mL Cefixime suspensions, both locally manufactured and imported, in Kabul City. A review of the literature indicates that no similar research has been conducted in Afghanistan under the title “Evaluation of the Physical Parameters of 100 mL Cefixime Suspensions (Locally Manufactured and Imported).” However, several related studies have been reported internationally, presenting a range of findings.

In this study, we specifically examined key physical characteristics, including label specifications, suspension volume, pH, and sedimentation volume. By contrast, international studies have assessed these parameters with slight variations and often with different objectives, such as evaluating viscosity, active ingredient release, or assay determination in addition to pH and sedimentation volume (Mahmood, et al., 2023). Moreover, some international investigations combined physical, chemical, and biological analyses;

however, their broader scope or workload occasionally led to the omission of certain fundamental physical parameters (Balogun-Agbaje, et al., 2024). Therefore, our study provides a focused assessment of these essential physical properties, which may serve as a baseline for future pharmaceutical quality evaluations in Afghanistan.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This research was conducted to evaluate the physical parameters of both locally manufactured and imported Cefixime suspensions available in Kabul City. Cefixime, a broad-spectrum third-generation cephalosporin antibiotic developed in the 1980s, exerts its antibacterial effect by inhibiting the transpeptidase enzyme during bacterial cell wall synthesis, thereby preventing cell wall formation. Cefixime remains widely used for the treatment of various bacterial infections, including those resistant to other β -lactam antibiotics. It is marketed in several dosage forms—tablets, capsules, chewable tablets, and oral suspensions. In this study, the emphasis was placed on the oral suspension dosage form, with an evaluation of key physical characteristics such as pH, sedimentation volume, and suspension volume. The findings highlight the importance of routine monitoring of these parameters to ensure product quality, stability, and patient compliance. Based on the results, it is recommended that:

Regulatory authorities establish standardized protocols for routine physical quality testing of both imported and locally manufactured suspensions.

Local manufacturers strengthen their quality control procedures, with particular attention to fundamental physical properties.

Future research expand beyond physical evaluation to include chemical and microbiological assessments for a more comprehensive quality profile.

Healthcare institutions collaborate with academic researchers to build a national database on pharmaceutical product quality in Afghanistan.

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